

State-Dependent Interventions in Human-AI Interactions through Input-Output Hidden Markov Models

Patrick Hendershott (Candidly)

Ben Levine (Candidly)

Abstract

Conversational AI systems increasingly mediate high-stakes decisions, yet we lack models of how AI behavioral choices affect user engagement within a conversation. The challenge is that user engagement is latent: we observe what users type, not what they think. A user who needed reassurance but received a call to action does not simply ignore the message. Their disposition toward the entire conversation changes. Because engagement is unobserved and dynamic, the effect of any AI behavior is state-dependent, and models that average over latent states systematically obscure the effects that matter most.

We model AI-human advisory conversations as governed by latent engagement regimes that evolve through the interaction and respond to the AI’s behavioral choices. Using an Input-Output Hidden Markov Model (IO-HMM) fitted to 2,408 real conversations with an AI financial advisor, we recover four interpretable engagement states with abandonment rates ranging from 22% to 70%. The same AI action, deploying a visual artifact for instance, seems to have favorable effects on transitions in one state and unfavorable effects in another. This state-dependence is invisible to static models, which predict conversation-level outcomes well but cannot explain why. The AI’s controllable response features serve as transition covariates, defining a policy surface for state-conditioned intervention design.

Keywords: input-output hidden Markov model, conversational AI, latent engagement dynamics, state-dependent interventions, human-AI interaction

1 Introduction

Consumers increasingly use conversational AI systems to make important financial, purchasing, and service decisions. Amazon’s Rufus shopping assistant reached over 300 million users in 2025, generating \$12 billion in incremental annualized sales; shoppers who engaged with Rufus were 60% more likely to complete a purchase (Amazon, 2025). Bank of America’s Erica virtual financial assistant has surpassed 3.2 billion client interactions across 50 million users, averaging 58 million interactions per month (Bank of America, 2025). Each conversation ends one of two ways: the user’s question is addressed (resolution) or the user disengages without an answer (abandonment). Static models can predict which of these outcomes a conversation ends in with high accuracy, but the same features applied turn-by-turn predict at near-chance levels (Section 3). Outcomes are predictable in aggregate while the turn-level mechanism that produces them remains latent, which motivates a dynamic model of the conversation.

This paper moves from predicting conversation outcomes to estimating how AI responses produce them at each turn. We treat the user’s engagement disposition as a latent state that evolves across the conversation and AI response characteristics as inputs that shift it.

We apply and adapt an Input-Output Hidden Markov Model (IO-HMM). Its input-output structure treats AI response characteristics as transition covariates and user-side signals as emissions, so the estimated transition coefficients tell us, for each latent state, which AI actions shift the user’s trajectory favorably. The paper contributes two things: a framework for estimating state-dependent effects of AI behavior from observational conversation data, and the empirical finding that the same AI action seems to have opposite effects depending on the user’s state, which together give a state-conditional policy surface a designer can act on.

This pattern shows up across the AI behaviors we test: the same response can shift transitions in opposite directions depending on the state the user is in, so any uniform policy has favorable effects for some users and unfavorable effects for others. Once a conversation reaches the disengaged state, none of the AI behaviors we tested has a detectable effect on recovery, which means the response surface works only for keeping users away from that state.

2 Data and Setting

2.1 Cait and the Advisory Context

We study conversations from Cait, an AI financial advisor built by Candidly for student loans, college savings, and financial wellness. Cait conducts text-based conversations and can deploy interactive artifacts: calculators, product recommendations, and informational displays alongside natural language responses.

2.2 Outcome Labeling

Every conversation ends the same way: the AI sends a final message and the user disappears. We need to determine whether the user got what they needed (resolved) or gave up (abandoned). We do not observe abandonment or resolution directly. We develop a hybrid labeling pipeline that combines a rule-based decision tree with LLM-based classification. The decision tree resolves about half of conversations deterministically using clear signals: the user went on to use a recommended product, the user never responded after the AI’s first message, or the user’s final messages contain explicit confusion or frustration. For the rest, the decision tree identifies the relevant conversational pattern and uses it to construct a targeted prompt for an LLM judge, which evaluates whether the conversation reached resolution or was abandoned. These labels achieve 92.3% agreement with our human expert labelers (Figure A1).

2.3 Analysis Sample

Table 1 summarizes the labeled analysis sample. The data comprise 2,408 conversations from 1,953 unique users, totaling 10,045 AI turns.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the analysis sample.

Characteristic	Value
Conversations	2,408
Unique users	1,953
AI turns (observations)	10,045
Mean AI turns per conversation	4.2
Mean conversations per user	1.3
Resolved conversations	1,450 (60%)
Abandoned conversations	958 (40%)

3 Predicting Conversation Outcomes with Static Models

A *conversation* is a single session between one user and Cait, identified by a unique thread identifier. Each conversation consists of an alternating sequence of user messages and AI responses, beginning with the user’s first message and ending with the AI’s final response. A *turn* is a single AI response within a conversation, paired with the user message that immediately preceded it. Each AI turn constitutes one observation in the analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A conversation broken into turns. Each turn bundles the user prompt y_t that elicited the AI’s response with the AI response itself a_t , and constitutes one row in the analysis data.

We apply gradient boosted trees (GBM) and Lasso logistic regression to 24 features spanning AI response properties, user engagement signals, and conversation context, predicting outcomes at the conversation level and at the turn level (Table 2).

3.1 Thread-Level Prediction

At the conversation level, a gradient boosted model predicts resolution vs. abandonment with 0.90 AUC (where 0.5 is chance and 1.0 is perfect discrimination). The top predictors include AI behavioral features (substance ratio, topic continuity, QA alignment, complexity mismatch) and user engagement signals (message length, reading complexity, caps ratio). Both categories contribute meaningfully: conversation outcomes reflect a combination of what the AI did and how the user responded.

3.2 Turn-Level Prediction

The same features applied turn by turn collapse to 0.606 AUC (GBM) and 0.603 AUC (Lasso logistic). Both models surface the same top drivers but achieve near-chance discrimination. We can predict how a conversation ends from its aggregate features, but we cannot predict whether the conversation will resolve or abandon at any given turn. The gap between conversation-level and turn-level performance reflects how outcomes depend on the full trajectory of exchanges, which a single-turn snapshot cannot capture.

Table 2: Static prediction summary.

Model	Level	AUC	Sample
Gradient Boosted Model	Thread	0.898	849 train, 279 test
Gradient Boosted Model	Turn	0.606	3,585 turns
Lasso Logistic	Turn	0.603	3,585 turns

Note: These static prediction models were fit on the prior 818-conversation sample and have not been re-run on the expanded 2,408-conversation dataset of Table 1; the qualitative thread-level versus turn-level performance gap is the relevant motivation for the dynamic model that follows. Thread-level model uses 24 features on the 818-conversation sample, split 75/25 at the thread level. Turn-level models use the same feature set on 3,585 AI turns.

3.3 From Prediction to Dynamics

These results expose three gaps in static prediction. First, no model that scores turns in isolation can support real-time intervention. The 0.61 AUC at the turn level reflects a structural limit: a static turn-level model has no mechanism to integrate signal across the trajectory, which is precisely what an in-conversation decision requires. Second, conversation-level prediction is purely retrospective: it identifies which conversations went wrong, but only after they are over, too late for the system to intervene. Third, both models pool AI actions and user responses as undifferentiated features, with no structural role for who controls what. What these systems need is a model that can separate the AI’s controllable choices from the user’s responses, estimate how those choices shift the conversation’s trajectory, and identify where a different intervention would change the outcome.

4 Latent Engagement Regimes

4.1 Why an Input-Output HMM

An Input-Output Hidden Markov Model is built for exactly the requirements identified in Section 3. The hidden Markov structure models the conversation as a sequence of latent states, with a forward algorithm that produces state estimates from observable features at each turn. The input-output extension is what turns the model from descriptive to policy-relevant. A plain HMM’s transition matrix is a single fixed stochastic matrix applied regardless of what happens in the conversation: it could recover the same engagement regimes but would say nothing about what moves users between them. The IO split treats user-side signals as emissions and AI behavioral features as transition covariates, so the transition matrix becomes a function

of the AI’s behavioral features at each turn. The estimated transition coefficients are the policy surface the rest of the paper analyzes.

This approach builds on [Netzer et al. \(2008\)](#), who applied an IO-HMM to customer relationship dynamics where institutional actions had an enduring impact on transitions between latent loyalty states in alumni donation panels. We adapt the framework from repeat-purchase panels to intra-conversation dynamics, with the AI’s behavioral choices as the input features whose effects on state transitions we estimate.

4.2 Features and Model Structure

Table 3 defines the 15 features used in the IO-HMM, organized by their role in the model. The static models in Section 3 used a broader set of 24 features; the 15 here are those with a clear role in the IO-HMM’s emission-transition structure.

Table 3: IO-HMM feature definitions and sample means ($N=10,045$ AI turns across 2,406 threads).

Emission Features (User-Side, 5 features)		
Feature	Description	Mean
Caps ratio	Proportion of user message in capital letters	0.053
User message length	Token count of the prior user turn	13.1
QA alignment	Content-word overlap (Jaccard) between the current AI response and the prior user turn	0.036
User reading level	Flesch–Kincaid grade level of the prior user turn	7.0
Grounding ratio	Cumulative grounding acknowledgments divided by turn index, bounded $[0, 1]$	0.029

All emission features are per-turn-index centered before fitting (a turn-position fixed effect that removes structural turn-1 artifacts); means shown are on the raw scale.

AI Behavioral Features (Transition Covariates, 9 features)		
Feature	Description	Mean
Substance ratio	Proportion of response containing domain-specific content	0.977
Language density	Ratio of content words to total words	0.000
Function word match	Degree to which AI mirrors user’s function word patterns	0.068
Actionable phrase	Whether response contains a call to action	0.371
Artifact velocity	Rate of interactive artifact deployment	0.045
Cumulative artifacts	Total artifacts deployed so far in conversation	0.68
Boilerplate ratio	Proportion of response that is generic filler	0.017
Topic continuity	Semantic similarity between consecutive AI responses	0.044
Complexity mismatch	Gap between AI and user message complexity	-1.48

The emission features capture behavioral consequences of the user’s latent engagement: how much they

write, how complex their language is, signs of frustration or satisfaction. The transition covariates capture controllable properties of the system’s response: how substantive the content is, whether artifacts were deployed, how well the AI matched the user’s complexity.

4.3 Model Specification

Let z_t denote the latent engagement state at turn t , taking values in $\{1, \dots, K\}$. Let $\mathbf{y}_t \in \mathbb{R}^6$ denote the vector of user-side emission features observed at turn t , and let $\mathbf{a}_{t-1} \in \mathbb{R}^9$ denote the vector of AI behavioral features from the preceding turn.¹ The AI-side behavioral features \mathbf{a}_{t-1} drive the transition to the next latent state z_t , which in turn produces the user-side emission \mathbf{y}_t (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The IO-HMM unrolled across three consecutive turns.

Emissions. Conditional on the latent state, the user-side features follow a multivariate Gaussian distribution:

$$p(\mathbf{y}_t | z_t = s) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_t; \boldsymbol{\mu}_s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s) \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s$ are the state-specific mean vector and covariance matrix. Each state produces a distinct emission profile, allowing the model to identify states from the observable patterns in user behavior.

Transitions. The probability of transitioning from state s to state j is conditioned on the AI’s behavioral features from the previous turn via a multinomial logistic model:

$$P(z_t = j | z_{t-1} = s, \mathbf{a}_{t-1}) = \frac{\exp(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{sj}^\top \mathbf{a}_{t-1})}{\sum_{j'=1}^K \exp(\boldsymbol{\beta}_{sj'}^\top \mathbf{a}_{t-1})} \quad (2)$$

Each source state s has its own set of coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{sj}$, so the effect of a given AI action on the next state depends on the current state. This is the mechanism through which the model captures state-dependent

¹Although each turn-row carries both \mathbf{y}_t and \mathbf{a}_t (Figure 1), the IO-HMM conditions the transition into z_t on \mathbf{a}_{t-1} from the preceding turn: the user observes \mathbf{a}_{t-1} before producing \mathbf{y}_t , so AI features index with a one-turn lag relative to the emission.

intervention effects.²

Estimation. The model additionally requires an initial state distribution $\pi_s = P(z_1 = s)$, estimated from the data alongside the emission and transition parameters. All parameters are fitted jointly via Expectation-Maximization. The E-step computes two posterior quantities via the forward-backward algorithm:

$$\gamma_t(s) = P(z_t = s \mid \mathbf{y}_{1:T}, \mathbf{a}_{1:T}) \quad (3)$$

$$\xi_t(s, j) = P(z_{t-1} = s, z_t = j \mid \mathbf{y}_{1:T}, \mathbf{a}_{1:T}) \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma_t(s)$ is the posterior probability of occupying state s at turn t , and $\xi_t(s, j)$ is the posterior probability of transitioning from s to j between consecutive turns. The M-step updates emission parameters as γ -weighted sufficient statistics:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_s = \frac{\sum_t \gamma_t(s) \mathbf{y}_t}{\sum_t \gamma_t(s)} \quad (5)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s = \frac{\sum_t \gamma_t(s) (\mathbf{y}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s)(\mathbf{y}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s)^\top}{\sum_t \gamma_t(s)} \quad (6)$$

The transition coefficients update by maximizing the ξ -weighted log-likelihood with L_2 regularization ($\alpha = 0.01$):

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_s = \arg \max \sum_t \sum_j \xi_t(s, j) \log P(z_t = j \mid z_{t-1} = s, \mathbf{a}_{t-1}; \boldsymbol{\beta}_s) - \alpha \|\boldsymbol{\beta}_s\|_2^2 \quad (7)$$

where $P(z_t = j \mid z_{t-1} = s, \mathbf{a}_{t-1}; \boldsymbol{\beta}_s)$ follows the multinomial logistic form in Equation (2). We initialize emission parameters from K -means clustering. Convergence is declared when the log-likelihood changes by less than 10^{-4} between iterations.

Model selection. We restrict to the 1,716 conversations with at least two AI turns (692 single-turn conversations carry no transition information) and split 75/25 at the thread level (1,280 train, 436 test threads). We evaluate $K \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$ using BIC and held-out log-likelihood, and select $K=4$ for its combination of interpretable state profiles, strong BIC, and strong held-out log-likelihood. Table A1 reports the full comparison.

Static benchmark. To verify that transition dynamics add value beyond static clustering, we fit a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) over the same $K \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$ range using the same six emission features, assigning each turn to a cluster based on its features alone. At matched $K=4$, the IO-HMM outperforms the GMM by 0.53 nats per observation on held-out data (-6.75 vs. -7.29) and achieves a substantially better BIC (33,245 vs. 35,595; Table A1). Transition structure captures sequential information that single-turn clustering cannot recover at the same model complexity.

²A chi-squared test of conditional independence between z_{t-2} and z_t given z_{t-1} on the decoded state sequence yields $p = 0.24$ ($\chi^2 = 35.1$, dof = 30), consistent with the first-order Markov structure.

4.4 States

Table 4 summarizes the four recovered engagement states. The names (Engaged, Detailed, Guided, Disengaging) are our characterizations of each state’s behavior based on its emission profile and out-of-model signatures; the IO-HMM itself produces unlabeled latent classes. Panel A reports the state-conditional emission means the model was fit on; Panel B reports behavioral and outcome signals computed from features outside the IO-HMM covariate set.

Table 4: Four IO-HMM engagement states. Panel A reports emission means the model was fit on. Panel B reports behavioral and outcome signatures computed on features outside the IO-HMM emission and transition covariate set ($N=7,011$ AI turns across 1,280 labeled training threads).

	Engaged	Detailed	Guided	Disengaging
Panel A. IO-HMM emission means (model inputs, see Table 3).				
User message length (words)	12.0	37.4	11.3	9.2
User reading level (Flesch–Kincaid)	7.3	8.2	4.8	7.7
Caps ratio	.039	.186	.026	.058
QA alignment	.054	.054	.020	.001
Grounding ratio	.003	.089	.122	.000
Panel B. Out-of-model behavioral signatures and outcomes.				
<i>Dynamics</i>				
% of turns	52	7	17	23
Mean AI turns per thread (terminal state)	4.8	5.9	8.7	4.6
P(thread resolves ends here) (%)	78	73	73	30
<i>How the user interacts</i>				
User brings new info (%)	82	65	62	72
User discloses context (%)	17	17	11	9
<i>Downstream financial action (post-conversation, B2B users only³)</i>				
% users who explored a Candidly product	26	24	25	20
% users who activated a Candidly product	28	15	11	23

Note: Panel A shows the state-conditional emission means for the five features the IO-HMM was fit on (Table 3). Panel B shows signatures and outcomes computed from features the model was not fit on. Resolve and downstream rates are thread-level, using threads whose terminal turn is decoded into the named state.

Engaged has anchored emissions: moderate-length user messages, near-average reading level, and the highest QA alignment between user prompt and AI response of any state. Outside the model, users in Engaged are also the most active in the data, bringing new information and disclosing personal context at the highest rates of any state, with the highest in-conversation resolution of the four. The conversations are tight back-and-forths in which the user is putting the conversation forward and the AI is delivering on specifics. High user disclosure paired with the highest in-conversation resolution is the signature of a successful interaction with an AI financial advisor.

Detailed has the longest user messages by a wide margin and the highest reading level of any state. Outside the model, users in Detailed bring new information at moderate rates but disclose personal context as often as in Engaged. Where Engaged uses short messages in a quick back-and-forth, Detailed messages

are roughly three times longer, putting more content into each turn. Long messages dense with structured content and program-specific acronyms paired with high in-conversation resolution are the signature of a substantive advisory interaction with an AI financial advisor.

Guided has the lowest user reading level of any state, short user messages, and the highest grounding ratio. Outside the model, users in Guided bring new information at the lowest rate of any state. Guided’s terminating threads run the longest in the data, and the state self-transitions at 91%. The in-conversation resolution rate is 73%, similar to Engaged and Detailed, and this resolution is earned within the state itself.⁴ Guided is where the user has framed the question in earlier turns and the AI takes over to deliver the answer: a longer exchange in a simpler register, with grounded references and short user acknowledgments.

Disengaging has the lowest QA alignment between user prompt and AI response of any state and the shortest user messages. Outside the model, Disengaging’s in-conversation resolution rate is the lowest of any state at 30%. The state is recoverable: roughly half of continuations from Disengaging move back to Engaged at baseline, and Section 4.5 shows that calls to action significantly increase that recovery while reducing Disengaging’s self-transition rate. The conversations are exchanges where the user contributes short messages and the AI’s response addresses different content than the user’s prompt. These show a user who has stepped back from productive engagement but stays in the conversation, recoverable through the right AI behavior.

Each state carries meaningfully different user behavior, conversation length, in-conversation resolution, and post-conversation action, establishing the four states as fundamentally distinct conversational regimes. The next subsection examines how the AI’s controllable response features move conversations between these regimes.

4.5 AI Actions and State Transitions

The estimated effect of an AI response on a conversation depends on the state that conversation is already in. The same response seems to shift different conversations in opposite directions, and all nine AI behavioral features show this pattern.⁵ An experiment that applies one response style to every conversation and reports the average effect can show no effect at all, because the response has favorable effects in some states and unfavorable effects in others and those effects cancel.

Topic continuity at +1 SD significantly holds Engaged users in place, raising self-transition from 60% to 88%*** and cutting drift to Disengaging from 31% to 5%***; the same shift in Disengaging raises its self-transition from 47% to 55%*, locking users in the lowest-resolution state. Artifact velocity significantly destabilizes Detailed (self-transition from 50% to 34%***) and redirects users into Engaged and Guided; the same shift in Disengaging cuts recovery to Engaged from 48% to 32%** and raises the self-transition from 47% to 62%**.

⁴Roughly 90% of entries to Guided come from Engaged or Detailed, and return from Guided to either is rare (8% combined). To verify that the resolution is delivered during Guided, we truncate each Guided thread at the turn before Guided entry and re-run the labeling tree on the upstream portion; 65% of the originally-resolved Guided threads are labeled abandoned under this re-labeling, indicating that the substantive answer is produced within Guided itself.

⁵With 9 covariates across 4 states, overfitting is a concern. A reduced specification using only substance ratio, boilerplate ratio, and artifact velocity (same emission features, same 75/25 thread split) preserves the sign of every transition coefficient and yields worse held-out log-likelihood (−7.32 vs. −7.09 nats/obs), so the additional covariates carry out-of-sample signal.

Table 5: Transition matrices under baseline and selected AI behavioral features.

Action	From	Destination State			
		Engaged	Detailed	Guided	Disengaging
Baseline	Engaged	60.1	4.1	5.2	30.6
	Detailed	13.0	50.0	23.9	13.1
	Guided	1.9	6.7	90.9	0.5
	Disengaging	47.7	2.5	2.7	47.1
Substance ratio	Engaged	55.7	3.2	9.9	31.2
	Detailed	11.4	41.7	35.1	11.8
	Guided	9.6	11.6	77.9	0.9
	Disengaging	43.0	2.1	6.9	47.9
Boilerplate ratio	Engaged	63.4	4.5	2.7	29.5
	Detailed	13.8	51.7	34.2	0.4***
	Guided	2.7	5.1	91.9	0.4
	Disengaging	57.0*	3.0	1.3	38.7*
Actionable phrase	Engaged	74.1	4.7	3.7**	17.5
	Detailed	22.9*	49.8	25.7	1.5**
	Guided	31.4	4.1	61.4	3.1
	Disengaging	58.8**	3.9	2.3	35.1**

Note: Baseline reports the empirical conditional transition matrix from decoded paths. Each subsequent panel reports the matrix at +1 SD of the corresponding AI behavioral feature, holding all others at observed values. Rows are origin states; columns are destination states. Significance reported on each cell’s shift relative to the baseline panel: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

sign-reversals. A uniform “always maintain topic continuity” or “always deploy artifacts” policy would both strengthen and undermine user trajectories in roughly equal measure.

Guided’s defining property is its 91% self-transition rate, the highest of any state. Entries to Guided come from Engaged (5% per continuing turn) and Detailed (24%). Disengaging carries a different risk: entries come from Engaged at 31% per continuing turn and from Detailed at 13%, into a state where the in-conversation resolution rate is 30%; from Disengaging itself, 48% of continuations recover to Engaged and 47% stay. System design should therefore focus on two margins: preventing drift into Disengaging from Engaged or Detailed, and lifting the Disengaging \rightarrow Engaged recovery.

4.6 Bootstrapping and Model Validity

A single IO-HMM fit is vulnerable to both nonconvex EM initialization and label permutation under the symmetric likelihood. We resample threads with replacement 200 times, refit the full-covariate IO-HMM on each resample with three EM restarts to mitigate EM non-convexity, and align state labels across fits by Hungarian assignment on standardized stacked emission means and self-transition probabilities. Resamples are accepted only when all four states match the reference within a distance threshold; 99 of 200 resamples (49.5%) are accepted, with the rejected half most often failing to recover Detailed, which depends on a small tail of long high-complexity conversations. Every value in Table 4 and Table 5 reports the expectation across the 99 accepted resamples. Confidence intervals are computed as percentile bands across these resamples

(95% CI from the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile), and significance markers in Tables 5 and A2 are awarded when the bootstrap distribution of the per-resample paired shift between baseline and +1 SD excludes zero at the corresponding percentile threshold.

5 Discussion

5.1 Latent Context in Conversational AI

Discoverable conversational phases are well established in human dialogue research. Boyer et al. (2009) used HMMs on tutorial dialogue and found that tutoring sessions pass through latent phases that predict learning outcomes, a finding that generalizes naturally to advisory settings where an expert guides a non-expert through a problem. Chotimongkol (2008) used HMMs to learn the phase structure of task-oriented conversations, the closest structural analogue to advisory dialogue, showing that even without pre-specified stage labels the model recovers interpretable sequential structure. Fu et al. (2024) identified five counseling stages from text-based therapy transcripts that align with established therapeutic frameworks, demonstrating that latent phase recovery works in text-only, high-stakes settings.

We bring this framework to AI-mediated advisory conversations. The user carries a latent engagement disposition through the conversation that conditions how they respond to AI actions and governs whether the conversation succeeds or fails, and the four engagement regimes we recover establish the disposition as real and estimable from turn-by-turn observables. The input-output structure of our model also estimates how the controllable features of the AI’s response strategy shift users between regimes, so we recover both the phases users pass through and the system behaviors that move them between phases.

The transition estimates in Section 4.5 suggest that the controllable AI response surface has powerful effects on engagement dynamics, and those effects are state-conditional. A response policy that deploys any single AI behavior uniformly would have favorable effects on some conversations and unfavorable effects on others, so the right object of optimization is the conditional mapping from latent state to behavior. A state-aware policy therefore operates on two margins: preventing drift into Disengaging from Engaged or Detailed, and lifting the Disengaging → Engaged recovery.

5.2 Implications for Experimentation

Our observational IO-HMM recovers a candidate policy surface, but it does not yet support a causal claim. The AI’s behavioral features are endogenous to the conversation: the response strategy is conditioned on message content and conversation history, so the estimates conflate selection with the causal effect of the action. A second concern is that observational correlates can diverge from causal responsiveness, as Ascarza (2018) showed in retention marketing where targeting policies built on observational risk estimates were ineffective because the customers most likely to churn differed from the customers most responsive to a retention offer. A similar gap can exist here between the behaviors that co-occur with favorable transitions and the behaviors that would cause them under intervention.

Hitsch et al. (2018) address this challenge in the targeting-policy literature. They show that observational estimates can guide the construction of a candidate policy, which a randomized experiment then validates: the randomized comparison recovers the policy’s causal value even when the estimates that produced it are biased.

The experiment randomly assigns conversations to a state-aware policy or the default production policy. The IO-HMM’s forward algorithm classifies each turn’s latent state from the five emission features in real time, giving the state-aware arm a running estimate of the user’s current phase. The state-aware arm applies rules derived from the transition estimates: when the user is in Engaged or Detailed, it deploys the behaviors that significantly reduce drift to Disengaging; when the user reaches Disengaging, it deploys the behaviors that significantly lift recovery to Engaged and suppresses behaviors that significantly worsen recovery. The primary targets are preventing drift into Disengaging from Engaged or Detailed and lifting Disengaging → Engaged recovery.

The outcomes relevant to the advising context are in-conversation resolution, which captures whether the user’s financial question was addressed, and post-conversation product exploration and activation, which capture whether the advising surfaced a relevant financial action. If the state-aware arm keeps users in the productive states more often than the control, both outcomes should improve: resolution rises through fewer Disengaging terminations, and downstream product action rises through more time spent in states whose signatures (higher user disclosure, higher new-information share, more grounded content) predict productive advising trajectories. A null treatment effect would suggest that the state-conditional correlations we estimate do not transfer to interventions.

6 Conclusion

Conversational AI systems operate without access to the latent engagement context that governs conversation outcomes. Users carry a latent engagement disposition through the conversation, and the same AI action has opposite estimated effects depending on that disposition. Our IO-HMM recovers four engagement regimes from real advisory conversations and connects them to the controllable features of the AI’s response strategy, identifying which behaviors appear to sustain engagement and which appear to destabilize it.

Four findings stand out. The same AI behavior produces favorable estimated effects in one state and unfavorable estimated effects in another, so a uniform response policy works against itself across the conversation. The dominant dynamics are the drift into Disengaging (31% per turn from Engaged, 13% from Detailed) and the 48% Disengaging → Engaged recovery, both responsive to specific AI behaviors. Guided is the absorbing state in the model, with 91% per-turn self-transition and in-conversation resolution delivered within the state itself. And the Disengaging state reveals what a failing AI financial advisory conversation looks like: a passive user (shortest messages of any state) paired with misaligned AI responses (lowest QA alignment of any state) produces a far lower resolution rate, marking advisor-user mismatch as the observable signature of failure.

These findings define a policy surface: a mapping from latent state beliefs to AI response characteristics

that the system designer controls. The natural next step is to test whether a state-aware system, one that estimates the user's engagement disposition in real time and conditions its behavior accordingly, outperforms the current state-unaware approach. The IO-HMM provides both the theoretical framework and the practical machinery to run that experiment.

Appendix

Table A1: IO-HMM vs. GMM model comparison across $K \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

K	Model	Test LL/obs	BIC	Δ LL/obs
2	IO-HMM	-7.54	36,515	+0.23
	GMM	-7.77	37,693	
3	IO-HMM	-7.13	34,462	+0.36
	GMM	-7.49	36,231	
4	IO-HMM	-6.75	33,245	+0.53
	GMM	-7.29	35,595	
5	IO-HMM	-6.15	29,979	+1.07
	GMM	-7.22	34,988	

Note: This model selection comparison was conducted on the prior dataset and has not been re-run on the expanded 2,408-thread sample of Table 1; the qualitative conclusion (the IO-HMM dominates the static GMM at every K , and $K=4$ is the most seed-stable, interpretable choice) is the basis for selecting $K=4$ in the new fit reported in Tables 4–5. Both models use the same emission features, train/test split (75/25 at thread level), and random seed. Test LL/obs is the mean log-likelihood per observation on held-out data (higher is better). Δ LL/obs is IO-HMM minus GMM (positive favors IO-HMM). BIC is computed on training data (lower is better). The IO-HMM achieves better fit and lower BIC at every K . $K=2$ and $K=3$ fit substantially worse on both metrics. $K=5$ improves fit further, but the additional state blurs the most populated boundary across random initializations, with no consistent regime emerging. We select $K=4$ as the specification with the best combination of fit and seed-stable, interpretable state profiles.

Figure A1: Outcome labeling pipeline. Gray nodes are heuristic (deterministic); blue nodes are LLM judges (Claude Sonnet 4, temperature = 0). Conversations enter at the left; the first matching branch assigns the label. 92.3% agreement with human expert labelers.

Table A2: Transition matrices for remaining AI behavioral features (continued from Table 5).

Action	From	Destination State			
		Engaged	Detailed	Guided	Disengaging
Language density	Engaged	51.2	2.8***	4.5	41.6
	Detailed	10.5	49.2	20.0	20.3
	Guided	12.6	5.8	78.7	2.9
	Disengaging	41.3**	2.3	2.6	53.7**
Function word match	Engaged	67.2	6.6	2.9*	23.4
	Detailed	9.5**	58.3*	21.1	11.1
	Guided	11.9	23.9**	63.2***	0.9
	Disengaging	78.9**	1.0	0.9*	19.1**
Artifact velocity	Engaged	48.1	3.5	3.7	44.8
	Detailed	22.7	33.7***	30.8	12.8
	Guided	4.7	6.5	76.9	11.9
	Disengaging	32.1**	3.7	2.6	61.6**
Cumulative artifacts	Engaged	71.0	5.0	4.9	19.1
	Detailed	14.5	54.2	14.3**	17.0
	Guided	33.1	4.3	55.6	7.0
	Disengaging	60.3*	3.6	2.5	33.6*
Topic continuity	Engaged	88.1***	3.8	3.4	4.7***
	Detailed	23.1***	38.6***	27.2	11.1
	Guided	0.9	7.7	89.8	1.6
	Disengaging	40.5	2.9	1.4	55.2*
Complexity mismatch	Engaged	83.9**	2.9	7.0	6.2**
	Detailed	17.7	59.5*	19.0*	3.9***
	Guided	1.3	2.4***	94.1	2.2
	Disengaging	70.9**	3.4	2.5	23.2***

Note: Each panel shows the empirical conditional transition matrix shifted to +1 SD of the corresponding AI behavioral feature, holding all others at observed values. Rows are origin states; columns are destination states. Significance reported on each cell's shift relative to the baseline panel in Table 5: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

References

- Amazon. (2025). Fourth quarter 2025 earnings report.
- Ascarza, E. (2018). Retention futility: Targeting high-risk customers might be ineffective. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 55(1), 80–98.
- Bank of America. (2025). A decade of AI innovation: BofA's virtual assistant Erica surpasses 3 billion client interactions. Press release, August 2025.
- Boyer, K. E., Phillips, R., Wallis, M., Vouk, M., & Lester, J. (2009). Discovering tutorial dialogue strategies with hidden Markov models. *Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED)*.
- Chotimongkol, A. (2008). *Learning the structure of task-oriented conversations from corpus data*. Ph.D. thesis, Carnegie Mellon University.
- Fu, C., Zheng, Y., & Zhang, Z. (2024). Using hidden Markov models to reveal in-session stages in text-based counselling. *npj Mental Health Research*.
- Hitsch, G. J., Misra, S., & Zhang, W. W. (2018). Heterogeneous treatment effects and optimal targeting policy evaluation. Working paper, University of Chicago Booth School of Business.
- Netzer, O., Lattin, J. M., & Srinivasan, V. (2008). A Hidden Markov Model of customer relationship dynamics. *Marketing Science*, 27(2), 185–204.
- Stephens, M. (2000). Dealing with label switching in mixture models. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Statistical Methodology)*, 62(4), 795–809.